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From Toilet to Field - Time to See Human Sanitary Waste with Fresh Eyes

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Flush toilets have been a triumph of progress, securing clean living environments in their time. Still, it seems a little crazy that our daily outputs - urine and feces - are flushed away with clean, drinkable water. After that, wastewater treatment aims to separate clean water back into circulation. The process consumes energy and money.

Centralized wastewater treatment makes sense in many ways: it enables efficient processing of wastewater from thousands of people and industries. But some of these nutrients could be recovered and utilized before they even reach the treatment plant.

The Power of Urine - We Should Develop Separate Collection

Separately collecting urine offers an opportunity to use its nutrients as they are, without dilution or re-separation. For many Finns, dry toilets are familiar from summer cottages, and they work well without water. A composting toilet produces nutrient-rich material that can be used in the yard. So why aren't waterless or low-water toilet solutions more common? There are many reasons: decentralized collection and its small scale challenge logistics, and maintaining a second system alongside the current wastewater infrastructure can feel unnecessary.

However, wastewater treatment causes emissions and takes up land area. There is demand for recycled nutrients and fertilizers, but sewage sludge can contain various harmful substances. Could human waste be collected and processed separately on a larger scale - for example in new buildings, new residential areas, festivals, and events? This way, we could avoid contaminants that come with industrial wastewater and save water at the same time.

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And What About Us Humans - Are We Ready for Change? Is the general public ready to use different, separating toilets or accept fertilizers made from human waste?

Will Legislation Bend, or Will Human Minds Resist?

Challenges remain. For example, legislation may not recognize separately collected human sanitary wastes as raw materials for fertilizer products. There can also be differences between EU member states. Among EU countries, only Austria allows the sale of fertilizer made from urine, as do Switzerland and Liechtenstein. Clear frameworks are needed to promote nutrient recycling.

And what about us humans - are we ready for change? Is the general public ready to use different, separating toilets or accept fertilizers made from human waste? Using human-derived waste as fertilizer can face strong psychological and cultural resistance. The idea that food grows from human waste may feel unpleasant to many.

The Road Ahead

If these challenges are solved, human-based fertilizers could open the door to more sustainably produced food and cleaner waters. Is it time to see waste with fresh eyes?

These themes are explored in depth in the P2Green project, where, for example, a pilot site in Gotland, Sweden, processes urine collected from festivals into fertilizer for barley cultivation. The harvest is used to brew beer - which in turn is sure to increase the need for toilets - a perfect, or at least exemplary, nutrient cycle!

Disclaimer:

This blog post has been originally published on November 20, 2025 in Finnish on Luke's website: <https://www.luke.fi/fi/blogit/pontosta-pellolle-aika-katsoa-jatoksia-uusin-silmin>

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